

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ABDOMINAL
CIRCUMFERENCE VERSUS HEAD CIRCUMFERENCE FOR
PREDICTION OF ASSYMETRIC INTRAUTERINE GROWTH
RESTRICTION**¹Dr. Shafaq Zaman, ²Dr. Tehreem Tariq, ³Dr. Iqra Sajjad¹PMDC # 93775-P., ²PMDC # 95297-P., ³PMDC # 93510-P.**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) remains as one of the most common complication in females of reproductive age. Untreated individuals may develop condition of infertility initiated by the condition IUGR.

Objective(s): Aim of the study is to measure the accuracy of ultra-sonographic determination of TCD/AC vs HC/AC and state more sensitive and specific measure for the determination of IUGR

Methodology: For the current study (N=405) pregnant females with gestational age between 18-35 weeks and no congenital anomaly were substituted. All of the samples were obtained after getting informed consent at Hospital . Ultra-sonographic determination of BPD, FL, TCD, AC, HC and EPW were measured and subjected to analysis for the findings.

Results: Findings of the study state that among all of the measures determination of ratio of TCD/AC were most significant it shows the area under curve (AUC) to be about 0.911 in case of TCD/AC which is significantly higher as compared to that of HC/AC (0.652). Moreover, specificity and sensitivity of the ratio remained significantly higher for TCD/AC (88%, 69%) respectively as compared to all other gynecological measures. It shows that the best cut-off value of TCD/AC ratio is 14.3%.

Conclusion(s): Study concludes on the basis of analysis of the measures obtained from the pregnant females that ratio of TCD/AC was more accurate as compared to the ratio of HC/AC. As signified by the literature the said ratio is far more helpful in the determination of IUGR in early stages in pregnant females.

Keywords: Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), Trans-cerebellar Diameter (TCD), Femur Length (FL), Biparietal Diameter (BPD).

Corresponding author:**Dr. Shafaq Zaman,**PMDC # 93775-P. Email: star920@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Shafaq Zaman et al., *Comparative Analysis Of Abdominal Circumference Versus Head Circumference For Prediction Of Assymetric Intrauterine Growth Restriction.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) is believed to affect a large number of infants worldwide especially in the developing countries [1] Fetuses suffering from IUGR are at a greater stake to develop cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and hypertension as compared to the normally grown fetuses. The condition can be well understood with the help of Doppler ultrasound examination that includes study of different vessels i.e., maternal uterine arteries and fetal umbilical arteries for placenta, percordial veins for the cardiac effects of placental dysfunction and middle cerebral artery (MCA) for the preferential brain perfusion. [3] Gestation period can be defined as the time period the infant has spent in the womb of mother or it may be defined as the measurement in weeks of the time period of pregnancy. Time period is calculated from the last menstrual period (LMP) to the date of examination. Time period for the full term pregnancy may last up to 42 weeks. During the period of gestation fetal growth is monitored that helps in planning of delivery and overcoming the complications that one can impart during the course of the pregnancy. [4] Accurate assessments of the gestational age is very crucial in the identification of preterm labor and for post-dated deliveries. Standard method for such determinations include antenatal ultrasound assessment based upon the different fetal parameters gestational age can be measured and can be compared with the reference ranges to look for the fetal growth. The accuracy in the measurement of the gestational age decreases as the fetal age advances from second to third trimester. Accuracy in the measurement of the fetal age is thus maximum in the first trimester. [4] One of the most common problem number of obstetricians go through the medical practice includes assessment of fetal maturity for the persisting and prolonging problems in pregnancy. Complications such as, pregnancy induced hypertension (PIH), diabetes, fetal distress and Rh incompatibility may lead to the development of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Methods employed for the prediction of gestational age and expected delivery date includes clinical examination, history of menstrual cycle, perception of fetal movement and calculation of biparietal diameter (BPD), femur length (FL), LMP, EDD etc. Apart from the fact that history of menstrual cycle and LMP is quite misleading in the determination of gestational age. Ultrasonography (USG) helps in the evaluation of the duration of pregnancy based on the measurement of fetus where size is the indicator of menstrual age. Various parameters that are employed for such determination includes biparietal diameter (BPD), head circumference (HC), abdominal circumference (AC) and femur length (FL).⁵

Whereas, increased variability in the parameters is observed with increasing gestational age. Measurement of another parameter like transverse cerebellar diameter (TCD) is becoming more accurate in the assessment of gestational age especially in the cases where the last menstrual cycle is not known. Thus, it is kept essential to determine the fetal growth restriction antenatally as it remains associated with the increased perinatal mortality and morbidity (Lerner, 2004). Similarly, biparietal diameter (BPD), head circumference/abdominal circumference (HC/AC) ratio is determined for the fetal maturity if the exact gestational age is known. TCD emerges to be one effective parameter in the fetal growth retardation. The IUGR fetuses demonstrate a temporally related, consistent pattern of abnormal Doppler velocimetry changes in a number of vessels for the weeks preceding delivery. Worsening of the pattern of flow in the UA, identified by the AEDF (absent end diastolic flow), and a persistent dilatation of the MCA is usually observed. These represent an early stage of progressive placental disease. Abnormal central circulatory changes consisting of changes in the ductus venosus waveform and in the outflow tract of the aorta and pulmonary artery are also observed but are seen in late stages of uteroplacental insufficiency. [6]

OBJECTIVE(S):

Current study aims to find out the diagnostic accuracy of sonographic measures transcerebellar diameter/abdominal circumference versus head circumference/abdominal circumference for prediction of assymetric intrauterine growth restriction.

HYPOTHESIS:

H₀: Diagnostic accuracy of Transcerebellar Diameter/Abdominal Circumference and Head Circumference/Abdominal Circumference may be equal in cases of IUGR on ultrasonography.

H₁: Diagnostic accuracy of Transcerebellar Diameter/Abdominal circumference is not equal to Head Circumference/Abdominal Circumference in cases of IUGR on ultrasonography.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design: Cross-sectional analytical

1. Setting:

2. Study Duration: 9 months

3. Sample Size: $n = z^2_{1-\alpha/2} S_N(1-S_N)/L^2 * \text{Prevalence}$
n= 405

i. prevalence= 0.1

ii. S_N= 0.88

iii. $L(\text{precision}) = 0.1$

4. Sample selection:

1) Inclusion Criteria:

- Gestational age between 18-35 weeks determined by first trimester scan
- Pregnant females with singleton pregnancy
- No congenital anomaly
- Favourable lie which facilitates posterior fossa visualisation and TCD measurement

2) Exclusion criteria:

- Females with gestational diabetes mellitus
- Mothers with history of fever in first trimester
- Females having history of irregular cycles
- Females having history of preterm birth

RESULTS:

The statistical analysis of the collected data for study suggests that TCD/AC almost remain constant in NON-IUGR fetuses with a very minor variation showing a minimal increase from 12.06 to 12.86 with increasing gestational age. Having a mean value of 12.46 and standard deviation of 0.4. However it was observed that TCD/AC ratio increases minimally from 13.32 to 15.44 in IUGR fetuses in relation to increasing gestational age with a mean value of 14.38 and a standard deviation of 1.06. Thus it was concluded that fetuses having TCD / AC ratio above 14.38 are at high risk for developing IUGR thus setting TCD/AC = 14.38 as the bench mark that distinguishes between IUGR and NON-IUGR fetus. PPV and NPV of TCD/AC was found to be 86% and 73% respectively. Sensitivity and specificity of TCD/AC was found to be 69% and 88% respectively. Area under curve as determined from ROC curve for TCD/AC ratio was found to be 1.009.

The analysis for the data collected for HC/AC ratio showed minimal increase with increasing gestational age thus HC/AC ratio ranges between 1.01 as the minimum value and 1.12 as maximum value in NON-IUGR fetuses with a mean value of 1.06 and a standard deviation of 0.05. There is a minimal rise in HC/AC ratio as the gestational age of the fetus increases both in IUGR and NON-IUGR cases. In IUGR fetus HC/AC ratio ranged between 1.04 and 1.16 with a mean value of 1.10 and a standard deviation of 0.06. Thus the mean value of HC/AC ratio in NON-IUGR found to be 1.05 when compared to the mean value of HC/AC ratio in IUGR fetuses i.e. 1.10, it is not much different in two groups. The PPV and NPV of HC/AC ratio was calculated to be 53% and 37%. Specificity and sensitivity of HC/AC ratio was calculated to be 41% and 49% respectively.

Area under curve for HC/AC ratio as determined from ROC curve was found to be 0.009.

Thus in the light of above findings the PPV, NPV, specificity and sensitivity of PCD/AC ratio (86%, 73%, 88% and 69% respectively) are higher than the PPV, NPV, specificity and sensitivity of HC/AC ratio (53%, 37%, 41%, 49% respectively). Area under curve for TCD/AC ratio (1.009) as determined from ROC curve construction and analysis is very high as compared to area under curve for HC/AC ratio (0.009).

So in the perspective of all these findings TCD/AC ratio can be considered to have a much higher diagnostic accuracy as compared to HC/AC ratio in cases of asymmetric IUGR.

DISCUSSION:

Intrauterine growth restriction is a major neonatal health issue. The term IUGR generally should be assigned only to those fetuses with birth weight or birth estimated fetal weight below the 10th percentile for given gestational age (GA) with a pathologic restriction of fetal growth. Fetuses with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) or small for gestational age (SGA) newborns are at increased risk of perinatal morbidity and mortality. In medical literature, IUGR and small for gestational age (SGA) terms are usually used interchangeably but slight difference exists between them. SGA are newborns whose birth weight is less than the 10th percentile for gestational age as per the population growth charts. SGA can be moderate or severe if it is moderate than birth weight would be from 3rd or 10th percentile and if it is severe then birth weight would be less than the 3rd percentile.

IUGR is found to be the communal outcome of maternal, placental, fetal or genetic factors. Besides an assessment of maternal factors for IUGR, SGA subgroups were also investigated for possible risk factors in this study. IUGR can also be caused by the combination of any of these factors. Symmetric IUGR fetuses may present at an earlier stage in gestation and incidence of total Symmetric IUGR are 20 to 30%. On antenatal scanning head circumference, Abdominal circumference, Biparietal diameter and Femur length are observed to be proportionally reduced while on the other hand cell number is reduced and cell size is normal. In Symmetrical IUGR features of malnutrition are less pronounced and prognosis will be poor. On the other hand, asymmetrical IUGR present at the later gestational stages and incidence of asymmetric IUGR are 70 to 80%. Abdominal circumference is

decreased while Biparietal diameter, Head circumference and Femur length will be normal. Cell number remains normal while cell size get reduced. The features of malnutrition are more pronounced and prognosis will be good. Maternal malnutrition and uteroplacental inadequacy causes asymmetric IUGR while congenital infections encountered early in pregnancy cause symmetric IUGR [26].

The fetal growth requires various hormones for its growth including adrenal hormones, thyroid, insulin and pituitary hormones. If there is any disturbance observed in these hormones it may disrupt the growth and development of the fetus. Insulin has mitogenic effects on cellular development so it is responsible to control the number of cells as well as responsible for uptake and consumption of glucose by body tissues and decreases breakdown of protein. Insulin deficiency will be responsible for IUGR as it acts as a signal of nutrient availability required for the growth and nourishment of fetus. Insulin deficiency results in the deficit uptake and utilization of nutrients²⁹. It has been observed in several clinical trials that the pancreatic agenesis of the fetus results in fetal hyperglycemia and decline in the concentration gradient of maternal fetal glucose which means fetal would not get its required amount of glucose and it became the leading cause of IUGR³⁰. Insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) is positively regulated by glucose supply in the fetus. Several clinical trials show that the IGF-1 has mitogenic properties which induce somatic cell growth and proliferation and it influences glucose transport and amino acid across the placenta.

There is a tremendous decrease in the growth of fetus if the expression of IGF-1 decreases [31]. In spite of proliferation, cell growth and glucose transport IGF-1 has a positive influence on brain growth which results in increase in neuronal number, oligodendrocytes, neuronal outgrowth, dendritic arborization and axon terminal fields [32]. In recent years, various preclinical trials show that the mutation in IGF-II results in the reduction in the fetus size [33,34]. The balance between the binding protein and the IGF enhances the cellular growth. The neuronal growth and whole body growth is affected by VIP which is another growth factor [35]. Hypothyroxinemia in the fetuses is the leading cause of developmental abnormalities which may include decreased consumption of oxygen and glucose oxides. Decreased consumption of oxygen and glucose oxides lessen the energy supply to fetus which is necessary for fetal growth and it also limits the tissue concentrations of IGF-1 [36, 37]. Fetal development and maturation of fetal organs including

glycogen deposition, gluconeogenesis, fatty acid oxidation, induction of surfactant production and release, structural maturation of the gastrointestinal tract, structural maturation of alveoli, increased expression of digestive enzymes, increased adrenal function, switch from fetal to adult hemoglobin synthesis and maturation of thymus, liver, kidney is also regulated by glucocorticoid hormone [38]. If the infant is symmetrical IUGR, then these infants can have other features such as associated dysmorphic facies, congenital anomalies (suggestive of chromosomal abnormality, intrauterine drug exposure) and also features of congenital viral infection, especially the TORCH group (microcephaly, petechiae, blue-berry muffin [purple skin lesions result of dermal erythropoiesis], cardiac defect, hepatosplenomegaly, intracranial calcification, chorioretinitis and cataracts). Intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR) is a chief risk factor for perinatal death and illness [39-42]. Due to asphyxia or uteroplacental insufficiency leads to fetal blood flow centralization with sparing of brain at the expense of other body parts [43]. Early IUGR detection is worthwhile in determining incidence of antenatal reconnaissance, optimum delivery time and primary neonatal management to evade perinatal morbidity and mortality [42]. Ultrasonography (USG) considered to be cornerstone for the fetal growth assessment [44]. Head circumference (HC), biparietal diameter (BPD), femur length (FC) and abdominal circumference (AC) are the most frequently used growth variables, but they are dependent on gestational age that restrict their application at growth extremes [45]. IUGR results in initial hepatic glycogen and subcutaneous fat depletion that leads to quick decrease in abdominal circumference [46]. Numerous studies have explored the two independent gestation age growth parameters including FL/AC ratio and TCD/AC ratio. FL/AC ratio is beneficial in early asymmetrical IUGR detection, while in symmetrical IUGR, both femur length and abdominal circumference are proportionately reduced [47]. The measurement carried out in the posterior cranial fossa is known as transcerebellar diameter (TCD). TCD is comparatively less affected by extrinsic compression and growth deviation due to hard bone walls surrounding the cerebellum and is also less affected as compared to head circumference signifying it as a better indicator for gestation age determination⁴⁶. In normally developing fetus, TCD is proportional to increasing gestation age. The present study has proven the increased value of TCD in diagnosis of IUGR as compared to HC and has also demonstrated its reliability in estimating the actual gestational age in growth restricted fetuses which is concurrent with

the study of Vinkestejin et al., [47] and Afshan et al., [48]. Femur length (FL) is the most commonly used growth parameter among all long bones. Villeret et al., [49] concluded that early asymmetrical IUGR, which is usually caused by uteroplacental insufficiency is associated with sparing of head and CRL while Wooet et al., [50] associated isolated short femur length with IUGR. Many studies reporting a good association between abdominal circumference (AC) and TCD have showed that the ratio TCD/AC is a stable, gestational age independent ultrasonographic parameter after crossing 20th gestational week [51]. Raised TCD/AC is supposed to show restricted fetal growth, so, may be useful for early fetal IUGR detection with better accuracy [52]. Meyer et al., [53] concluded that correlation between TCD and AC is high between 14 to 40 weeks but the ratio TCD/AC remain constant and has high sensitivity in detection of IUGR. In our study, TCD/AC values dispersed with the cut off value of 14.38%, specificity of 88% and sensitivity 69% which is low as compared to the cut-off values of the studies of Hussain et al., [54]; Dhumaleet al., [55]; Tongsonget al., [56] that were 15.49, 15.98 and 15.4 respectively. Bansal et al. [57]⁷ included 650 pregnant patients in his study with GA between 14 to 40 weeks established that TCD has a correlation to fetal gestation age. The sensitivity and specificity of TCD/AC in present study is relatively higher to that of HC/AC which remained 49% and 41% respectively. The correlation coefficient between GA and TCD was 0.972 with *p*-value <0.001. Direct association of TCD to progressing GA was witnessed in both normal and IUGR pregnancies [58]. Sharma et al., [59] revealed a significant correlation between TCD and gestation period. In IUGR pregnancies all parameters including BPD, HC & FL were showing disparity of > 3 weeks except TCD which in both groups were nearer to GA which is in support of our study. Benson et al., [60] and Divonet et al., [61] in their studies have shown good diagnostic validities for HC/AC ratio in predicting asymmetric IUGR with the specificity of 94% and 90% and sensitivity of 82% and 36% respectively while the specificity and sensitivity of HC/AC in current study is 70% and 78% respectively. Meyer et al., [62] studied 250 pregnant patients having high risk for growth retardation and 825 low-risk obstetric patients, the results of his study showed fetal TCD/AC ratio to be an accurate, gestational age independent method of identifying IUGR with better diagnostic validity compared to other morphometric ratios including HC/AC and FL/AC ratios. Hill et al., [63] assessed the reference curves for the HC/AC, FL/AC, TCD/AC ratios. The ratios were compared and it was found that TCD/AC was the most efficacious among all three ratios which

is in support of present study. The current study depicts the high specificity of TCD/AC (80%) as compared to HC/AC as well as also high sensitivity value in case of TCD/AC (91%) in comparison with HC/AC (78%) which is in accordance with the study of Bhimraoet al., [64] that have reported the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV & DA were 88%, 93.5%, 77.1%, 96.3% & 92.4% respectively for TCD/AC ratio versus 84%, 92%, 72.4%, 95.8% & 90.4% respectively for HC/AC ratio in predicting IUGR and concluded that TCD/AC ratio had a better diagnostic legitimacy and accuracy in comparison with HC/AC ratio in predicting asymmetric IUGR.

CONCLUSION:

Current study concludes that one of the most important complications come across during pregnancy is intrauterine fetal growth restriction. The growth-restricted fetus is at menace for adverse perinatal morbidity and mortality. Sonographic fetal parameters are regularly examined for gestational age prediction as well as to cope with fetal growth disturbances during pregnancies. Now-a-days, fetal ultrasonographic biometry is used for evaluating growth of fetus. Numerous diameters and circumferences including biparietal diameter (BPD), femur length (FL), head circumference (HC) and abdominal circumference (AC) have been deliberated regarding their association with the gestational age but these all are gestational age dependent. Two morphometric ratios, TCD/AC and HC/AC are considered to be independent gestational age parameters and can be used in predicting intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR) with better diagnostic precision. The current study has revealed a strong significant correlation between TCD and GA throughout the pregnancy time with constant TCD/AC in a normal pregnancy staying below 14.38 however it is observed to be higher than 14.38 in cases of asymmetric IUGR. Thus it could be used as a factor for IUGR detection. And the current study also makes it evident that TCD/AC ratio has a better diagnostic legitimacy and accuracy compared to HC/AC ratio in detecting asymmetric IUGR.

REFERENCES:

1. Franks S. Polycystic ovary syndrome. N Engl J Med. 1995;333(13):853861. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199603073341017
2. Eshre TR, Group A-SPCW. Revised 2003 consensus on diagnostic criteria and long-term health risks related to polycystic ovary syndrome. Fertil Steril. 2004;81(1):19-25. doi: 10.1093/humrep/deh098
3. Azziz R, Woods KS, Reyna R, Key TJ, Knochenhauer ES, Yildiz BO. The prevalence

- and features of the polycystic ovary syndrome in an unselected population. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2004;89(6):2745-2749. doi: 10.1210/jc.2003-032046
4. Arain F, Arif N, Halepota H. Frequency and outcome of treatment in polycystic ovaries related infertility. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2015;31(3):694-699. doi: 10.12669/pjms.313.8003
 5. Taylor AE. Polycystic ovary syndrome. *Endocrinol Metab Clin.* 1998;27(4):877-902. doi: 10.1016/S0889-8529(05)70045-1
 6. Esmailzadeh S, Andarieh MG, Ghadimi R, Delavar MA. Body mass index and gonadotropin hormones (LH & FSH) associate with clinical symptoms among women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Global J Health Sci.* 2015;7(2):101. doi: 10.5539/gjhs.v7n2p101
 7. Benetti-Pinto CL, Piccolo VR SB, Garmes HM, Juliato CRT. Subclinical hypothyroidism in young women with polycystic ovary syndrome: an analysis of clinical, hormonal, and metabolic parameters. *Fertil Steril.* 2016 ;99(2):588-592. doi: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2012.10.006
 8. Duijkers IJ, Klipping C. Polycystic ovaries, as defined by the 2003 Rotterdam consensus criteria, are found to be very common in young healthy women. *Gynecol Endocrinol.* 2010;26(3):152-160. doi: 10.3109/09513590903247824
 9. Muderris I, Boztosun A, Oner G, Bayram F. Effect of thyroid hormone replacement therapy on ovarian volume and androgen hormones in patients with untreated primary hypothyroidism. *Ann Saudi Med.* 2011;31(2):145. doi: 10.4103/0256-4947.77500
 10. Moghetti P, Tosi F, Castello R, Magnani CM, Negri C, Brun E, et al. The insulin resistance in women with hyperandrogenism is partially reversed by antiandrogen treatment: evidence that androgens impair insulin action in women. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 1996;81(3):952-960. doi: 10.1210/jcem.81.3.8772557
 11. Diamanti-Kandarakis E, Papavassiliou AG, Kandarakis SA, Chrousos GP. Pathophysiology and types of dyslipidemia in PCOS. *Trends Endocrinol Metab.* 2007;18(7):280-285. doi: 10.1016/j.tem.2007.07.004
 12. Valkenburg O, Steegers-Theunissen RP, Smedts HP, DallingaThie GM, Fauser BC, Westerveld EH, et al. A more atherogenic serum lipoprotein profile is present in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a case-control study. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2008;93(2):470-476. doi: 10.1210/jc.2007-1756
 13. Alsamarai S, Adams J, Murphy M, Post M, Hayden D, Hall J, et al. Criteria for polycystic ovarian morphology in polycystic ovary syndrome as a function of age. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2009;94(12):4961-4970. doi: 10.1210/jc.2009-0839
 14. Jonard S, Robert Y, Cortet-Rudelli C, Pigny P, Decanter C, Dewailly D. Ultrasound examination of polycystic ovaries: is it worth counting the follicles? *Hum Reprod.* 2003;18(3):598-603. doi: 10.1093/humrep/deg115